

GREENDT

D7.2 SUSTAINABILITY & EXPLOITATION PLAN

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Sustainability and Exploitation Plan outlines the strategic framework for ensuring the long-term impact and reuse of results from the GREENDT project. The strategy focuses on three pillars: (1) Strategic planning for post-project use of outputs and results, (2) Foster collaboration and partnerships to extend impact across sectors, and (3) Policy engagement strategy design to influence national and regional frameworks. This document includes details on the implementation, monitoring, and assessment of the activities planned to ensure the exploitation of the results and the sustainability of the project. The project team will regularly track progress towards these goals and revise the Sustainability and Exploitation Plan accordingly at M36.

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Acronyms

ASTI	Andijan State Technical Institute, Uzbekistan
CAGU	Central Asian University of Environmental and Climate Change Studies (Green University), Uzbekistan
CC	Creative Commons
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
EE	Environmental Engineering
EU	European Union
FEUGA	Fundación Empresa-Universidad Gallega, Spain
FSTU	Fergana State Technical University, Uzbekistan
GA	Grant Agreement
GREENDT	Implementing Environmental Engineering Master's Degrees through Sustainable Transition and Societal Change
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IP	Intellectual Property
IPVC	Polytechnic Institute of Viana do Castelo, Portugal
JizPI	Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, Uzbekistan
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KIUT	Kimyo International University in Tashkent, Uzbekistan
MEEPCC	Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection, and Climate Change in Uzbekistan
MHESI	Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan
MSc	Master's Degree
UAVEIRO	University of Aveiro, Portugal
UVIGO	Universidade de Vigo, Spain

1 Project summary

The primary goal of GREENDT is to empower staff and students in Uzbekistan Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the field of Environmental Engineering (EE) by transferring knowledge from European Union (EU) HEIs. This initiative aligns with the European Commission's Green Deal priority, aiming for a sustainable transition in environmental protection. The central focus is on enhancing the competencies and skills of Uzbekistan HEI students through the development of an innovative Master's degree (MSc). This program aims to foster the exchange of best practices, collaboration between Uzbekistan and European HEIs in EE, and boost students' entrepreneurship, thereby improving their employability through innovation.

The EU Green Deal represents a transformative roadmap toward climate neutrality by 2050, with international cooperation playing a key role in this agenda. By positioning GREENDT within this broader policy framework, the initiative contributes to the EU's strategy of global engagement and capacity-building in regions with untapped innovation potential. The replication of such good practices is critical, particularly in countries like Uzbekistan, where environmental challenges and new innovation ecosystems can benefit significantly from international collaboration. Other initiatives, such as Erasmus+ Capacity Building Projects and the Horizon Europe projects under the Twinning Green Deal, illustrate how knowledge transfer and institutional partnerships can drive systemic change. Embedding such practices in Uzbekistan not only supports local sustainable development goals but also opens opportunities for exploitation in related sectors such as renewable energy, circular economy, and smart infrastructure, reinforcing long-term sustainability and expanding the geographic reach of EU innovation leadership.

GREENDT also intends to contribute to societal development by establishing an EE Society. This society will facilitate accessible information, laboratories, and services through a collaborative network involving municipalities, industries, government agencies, and non-governmental organizations. The goal is to encourage the creation of specialized companies and provide a platform for sharing knowledge and resources. Additionally, GREENDT addresses the EE Nexus to support the modernization of key environmental players, making them more competitive and innovative. This approach ensures a sustainable transition, promotes green jobs, and contributes to building a climate-neutral society with a gender-transformative perspective. The structure of GREENDT involves a multi-actor setting, incorporating pivotal levers for change: HEIs and governance (policy).

The proposed actions under the GREENDT project include:

- Implementation of five EE MSc.
- Establish five EE laboratories to support research activities for MSc and provide services to industries and civil society.
- Development of an e-learning platform offering free information, online courses, and dedicated content to support MSc.
- Development of twelve new courses for the MSc program, including didactic materials.
- Development of a web platform focused on informing the public about the project life, meetings, training sessions, webinars, and important events.
- Establish an E-society platform in Uzbekistan to address environmental issues and foster collaborative solutions for sustainable development in Central Asia.
- Establish mobility agreements for MSc students.

2 Grant Agreement & Consortium

Agreement articles related to exploitation

The Grant Agreement (GA) “101179013 — GREENDT — ERASMUS-EDU-2024-CBHE” stipulates the conditions related to the exploitation and protection of results in Article 16.

- **Article 16.1. Background and access rights to results**

"Background" includes any existing data, knowledge, or IP (tangible or intangible) held before joining the project and needed for project implementation or exploitation of results. Beneficiaries must grant access to such background to each other and project participants, subject to the rules in Annex 5 of the GA:

- Beneficiaries must provide royalty-free access to their results to the granting authority, EU institutions, and national authorities for non-commercial, non-competitive use in developing, implementing, and monitoring EU or national policies and programmes.
- Access for national authorities must be governed by a bilateral agreement ensuring:
 - Use is limited to the intended purpose.
 - Confidentiality is maintained.
- The requesting authority must inform all other national authorities of the request.
- If continuity or interoperability is required by the call, beneficiaries must make their materials, documents, and results freely available online under open or open-source licences.
- If the background involves third-party rights, beneficiaries must ensure they can legally grant the necessary access.

- **Article 16.2. Ownership of Results**

The granting authority does not own any results created under the project. "Results" refer to any outcomes (data, knowledge, IP, etc.) from the project, regardless of whether they are protected or protectable.

- **Article 16.3. Use Rights of the Granting Authority**

The granting authority has a royalty-free, non-exclusive, irrevocable license to use non-sensitive materials from the project (like summaries, deliverables, media) for policy, communication, publicity, and dissemination, both during and after the project. Use includes copying, publishing, translating, editing, storing, archiving, authorizing third parties, and creating derivative works. These rights apply for the duration of the IP rights involved.

Beneficiaries must ensure that any third-party or moral rights (e.g., on images or voices) are properly cleared.

The Consortium Agreement, in its Article 12 “Ownership and property rights”, includes the following clauses related to the exploitation of project results:

- **Article 12.1** The ownership of all project results, including copyrights and intellectual property rights, as well as all reports and other documentation resulting from the action, shall be vested in the beneficiary, in compliance with the Grant Agreement.
- **Article 12.2** The Project Results that have been generated in collaboration shall be jointly owned by the Parties whose actions in the Project has led to the generation, invention or creation of the Result, in a proportion that must reflect the effective contribution of each party.

- **Article 12.3** The provisions of the joint ownership agreement shall be agreed separately between the joint owners.
- **Article 12.4** Materials already developed and brought into the project must remain property of the respective owner and may be only used within the scope of the project as templates of good practice. Copyrights shall be strictly safeguarded and permission for reproduction and scale of production has to be settled beforehand.

3 Sustainability and Exploitation Strategy

This document will set a strategic plan to exploit the results generated throughout the GREENDT project, contributing to their sustainability beyond the project's lifetime.

3.1 Introduction

Exploitation refers to the comprehensive set of processes aimed at maximizing the impact and sustainability of project results through their effective use. It includes a wide range of activities such as:

- The identification and categorisation of the different types of results generated by the project.
- The evaluation of intellectual property (IP) rights and protection strategies, where applicable.
- The coordination with project partners to define individual or joint exploitation interests.
- The identification of potential end-users, stakeholders, and target markets.
- The analysis of implementation needs and conditions for uptake.
- The presentation and promotion of results to potential users and beneficiaries.
- The negotiation of exploitation agreements, such as licensing or commercialization deals, where applicable.
- The search for funding and investment opportunities to support scalability.

Ultimately, exploitation ensures that project outcomes are not only disseminated but are also effectively transferred and integrated into relevant policies, practices, and markets at local, national, and international levels. These processes are elaborated in this document, D7.2, Sustainability and Exploitation Plan. Strategic communication efforts supporting exploitation are further detailed in D7.1, Communication and Dissemination Plan.

The following sections outline the strategic plan for exploiting GREENDT results, aligned with the project's goals and expected impact.

3.2 Exploitation Methodology

The Sustainability and Exploitation Plan presented in this document will be continuously reviewed and updated to ensure the long-term impact of the GREENDT project and the durability of its results beyond the project's official duration.

GREENDT's specific objectives and expected results aim to contribute to the project's primary goal: empowering Uzbekistan's HEIs in EE. The sustainability and exploitation strategy for GREENDT has been defined through a collaborative process involving all project partners, guided by internal consultations and aligned with the project's broader objectives under the Erasmus+ framework. This process began with the identification of the project's tentative Key Exploitable Results (KERs), which were initially discussed during the Kick-Off Meeting (KOM) as a first step towards addressing intellectual property (IP) management and exploitation planning. As indicated in Section 4 below, the consortium will build an exploitation roadmap, including a comprehensive KER analysis, categorising the results by type, and partners will jointly prioritise the results based on their potential for reuse, transferability, and long-term impact. Moreover, partners will jointly assess the most suitable open license for each result, balancing openness with protection of authorship and recognition. Where applicable, project partners will adopt Creative Commons (CC) licenses.

The table below summarizes the project's specific objectives, expected results, and the tentative KERs associated with them, as identified during the KOM in Month 2 (M2).

Table 1. GREENDT specific objectives, expected results, and tentative KERs

Specific Objective	Expected results	Tentative KERs	Future exploitation & IP
Develop an MSc curriculum aligned with the "Green Deal" in EE to enhance relevance for the labor market, industry, and EU partner HEI experiences.	Analysis of existing education standards.	EE MSc curriculum	To be defined in the Exploitation Roadmap, by M36
	1 ECTS-accredit (equivalent to 60 credits or a full year of study) of EE MSc.	EE didactic materials & online courses	
	12 new development courses for the MSc program + 5 new study programs + didactic materials.		
	Conditions for student mobility.		
Develop EE-Lab standards and establish EE-Labs at all 5 Uzbek HEIs, supporting research, scientific collaboration, and industry engagement.	5 new EE laboratories (KIUT, JizPI, FSTU, ASTI, CAGU).	EE-lab standards	To be defined in the Exploitation Roadmap, by M36
	Establish an E-Society in Uzbekistan to address environmental issues and foster collaborative solutions for sustainable development in Central Asia.	E-Society Platform	
Implement digital transformation in EE education and science, incorporating innovative methods and ICT-based teaching.	E-learning platform for EE, free for all learners.	E-learning platform for EE Custom methods for ICT-based EE teaching	To be defined in the Exploitation Roadmap, by M36

GREENDT will carry out the following actions to ensure an effective exploitation of the results towards their long-term sustainability:

- **Develop an Exploitation Roadmap** for the post-project phase, focusing on the exploitation pathways for each KER. It will explore the sustainability opportunities of the EE MSc programme and the EE learning platform, and a proposal for the long-term maintenance, hosting, and governance of the E-Society Platform and EE Labs in operational and financial terms. The beneficiary partners in WP4, in charge of establishing the E-Society Platform and the EE labs, will be key in defining the exploitation roadmap. The roadmap will be included in the second iteration of this document, in M36.
- **Monitor the impact-related KPIs and disseminate the achieved results to the interested stakeholders** (university lecturers, academic staff, current and prospective students, universities in partner countries, governmental and industrial communities).

Details will be included in D7.4 Dissemination Activities Intermediate Report (M18) and D7.5 Dissemination Activities Final Report (M36).

- **The GREENDT project website will be maintained and regularly updated** throughout the project's lifecycle, contributing to the effective dissemination of project results to relevant stakeholders. The website will be accessible for at least two years after the project ends, displaying updates from the e-learning and the E-Society platforms.

3.3 Sustainability Implementation & Collaboration Strategy

GREENDT embeds sustainability into its core approach, aiming to strengthen and expand cooperation with key stakeholders and relevant consortia within and beyond the HEI sector.

GREENDT aims to contribute to a robust cross-sector ecosystem to amplify the reach, relevance, and reuse of the project results. To do so, the project will carry out the following actions:

- **Promote the new MSc program in EE**, developed under GREENDT, across other HEIs through dissemination activities. It is expected that at least twelve additional MSc programs will be established after the project's completion. Uzbek academic staff trained at EU HEIs will be fully equipped to deliver high-quality instruction to MSc students using project-developed materials, with an anticipated sixty students enrolled annually.
- **Encourage the participation of stakeholders in the open-access E-Society Platform**, encouraging the academic, governmental, and industrial communities' active involvement. The E-Society Platform will serve as a sustainable platform for knowledge exchange and collaboration between EU and Uzbek stakeholders in the field of EE.
- **Explore the development of actions to monitor employment outcomes and inform the Uzbek HEIs**, accordingly, based on the assumption that sustainable impact requires alignment with labour market needs. These measures aim to reinforce the practical relevance and long-term demand for EE graduates in Uzbekistan and beyond.
- **Involve experts from MHESI, MEEPCC, and industry stakeholders to contribute insights through project seminars and during the establishment of EE laboratories.** Their ongoing involvement will help ensure that project results remain relevant and impactful in related industrial sectors. A minimum of five collaborative activities—including publications, exchange visits, and joint seminars—will be carried out between HEIs, industry actors, and policymakers, fostering ongoing cooperation.
- **Encourage stakeholders' active support to maintain the e-learning platform for EE** after the project ends. All new teaching materials will be made available via the GREENDT e-learning platform and integrated into the digital modules of participating Uzbek HEIs. These digital resources will remain operational beyond the project's lifespan.
- **Foster cooperation agreements between the European and Uzbek HEIs** participating in the project to promote academic exchange, mobility agreements, and joint activities among EE researchers and students beyond the project lifespan. During the project, EU and Uzbek HEIs will sign a sustainability agreement, with partner HEIs committing to long-term collaboration and demonstrating readiness to support student mobility by aligning academic regulations accordingly.

GREENDT's sustainability and exploitation strategy focuses on three interrelated actions:

- **Strategic planning actions**, including the development of a strategy for stakeholders to leverage the project outcomes, considering academic advancements, societal benefits, and economic gains.
- **Collaboration and Partnerships Actions**. Establish partnerships with relevant entities in industry, academia, and other sectors, pooling resources, sharing expertise, and maximizing the reach and impact of project results.
- **Policy Impact Actions**. Engage with policymakers and governmental bodies to inform policy based on the project results.

To maximise the impact of the exploitation activities and ensure GREENDT's sustainability, all partners must be involved in the proposed activities. More specifically, partners will have a central role in exploiting the KERs beyond the project's life through these actions:

- **Uzbek ministries (MHESI and MEEPCC)** will ensure the approval of the EE MSc program. Furthermore, MHESI will focus on the theoretical and academic aspects, while MEEPCC will contribute to its practical components. MHESI and MEEPCC's role for GREENDT's sustainability will also be related to exploring the implementation of EE-related scientific research projects and fostering the employability of EE MSc graduates.
- **Uzbek HEIs (ASTI, CAGU, FSTU, JizPI, and KIUT)** will be key in implementing the EE MSc, leveraging the study programmes, courses, didactic materials, and EE labs within their institutions, maintaining them over time. Moreover, FSTU will have a central role in the sustainability of the E-Society Platform, and KIUT will be responsible for the e-learning platform for EE.
- **EU HEIs (IPVC, UAVEIRO, UVIGO)** will leverage the academic collaboration established with their Uzbek counterparts, exchanging best practices through the E-Society Platform, exploring scientific cooperation opportunities, and promoting student mobility.

3.3.1 Policy impact actions development strategy

The following actions seek to help shape environmental and higher education policy through evidence-based recommendations from GREENDT.

- **Explore pathways to embed the EE MSc programmes into national qualification frameworks**, ensuring institutional commitment to continue them after funding ends. The accreditation strategy followed by GREENDT implies that all developed materials will be reviewed collaboratively by partner HEIs and submitted to the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan (MHESI). The new MSc program will be formally integrated into the State Educational Standard and classified under the national HE curriculum framework.
- **Engage directly with policymakers through the E-society platform** as a tool for community input, stakeholder feedback, and public engagement in policy dialogues around the advancement of environmental societal development in Uzbekistan.
- **Collaborate with EU delegations and Erasmus+ National Agencies to promote the transferability** of tools, methodologies, and structures to other relevant fields and academic programs across Central Asia and Eastern Partnership countries. The educational standards, curricula, and didactic models developed using digital tools will continue to function post-project through the established MSc programmes and e-learning infrastructure. An increasing number of HEIs in Central Asia are expected to adopt and expand upon these thematically aligned MSc offerings.

4 Implementation roadmap

The GREENDT project will implement its sustainability and exploitation strategy through a phased approach, aligned with project milestones and responsive to key decision points related to policy engagement, institutional readiness, and stakeholder feedback. The roadmap is monitored by WP7 and will be assessed at M18 and M30 based on implementation progress, as described in Section 5. Each of these actions is tied to a combination of deliverables, monitoring indicators and contingency plans. WP leads are responsible for coordinating implementation within the timeline and flagging risks or deviations during internal project reviews.

4.1 Exploitation Implementation Process

To ensure effective and strategic exploitation of project results, the GREENDT consortium will follow a four-phase approach:

- **KER Identification and Monitoring:** Initial mapping done by M2 and continuous monitoring of KERs' development, relevance, and uptake throughout the project, as described in Section 5.
- **KER Consolidation and Partner Alignment:** Partner meetings to align on how each KER will be exploited individually or jointly, and to define ownership and exploitation models. These meetings will take place after the foreseen checkpoints, by M18 and M30.
- **IPR Assessment and Strategy Definition:** Evaluation of IPR implications and definition of protection strategies (e.g., copyright, open licensing, trademarks) based on exploitation intentions. The conclusions will be presented at a final exploitation workshop for the project partners (M34-M36).
- **Promotion and External Uptake Facilitation:** For selected KERs with replication potential, partners will promote the results through specialized events, industry fairs, and outreach to targeted user communities. Details on dissemination activities are included in D7.1.

4.2 Initial list of sustainability activities

Building upon the exploitation activities of the project results, project partners commit to contributing to GREENDT's sustainability activities *beyond* the project's lifecycle. Before the project ends, the EU and Uzbek HEIs participating in GREENDT will sign a sustainability agreement, committing to take the necessary steps to ensure the sustainability of the EE academic cooperation.

The consortium will update the list of tentative sustainability actions, included in the table below, by M36, based on the outcome of the progress checkpoints at M18 and M30.

Table 2 List of sustainability activities

Key action	Partner	Activity beyond the project	Tentative contingency approach
Exchange of good practices	ASTI, CAGU, FSTU, IPVC, JizPI, KIUT, UAVEIRO, UVIGO	EU and UZ stakeholders will share good practices, experiences, and knowledge related to EE through the open E-Society Platform.	If platform funding ends, discussions will continue through academic networks or partner-hosted forums.

Key action	Partner	Activity beyond the project	Tentative contingency approach
Adoption of the EE MSc by other HEIs	ASTI, CAGU, FSTU, JizPI, KIUT, MEEPCC, MHESI	The EE MSc programme will be promoted in other HEIs.	Launch internal MSc programs and promote via academic networks if policy-level endorsement is delayed
Student mobility between Uzbek and UE HEIs	ASTI, CAGU, FSTU, IPVC, JizPI, KIUT, UAVEIRO, UVIGO	Partner HEIs will take the necessary steps regarding academic regulations to enable and foster student mobility.	If formal agreements stall, bilateral mobility will proceed via Erasmus+ or inter-institutional agreements.
Training EE students	ASTI, CAGU, FSTU, JizPI, KIUT,	Academic staff trained in EU HEIs will be qualified to teach MSc students by leveraging the new MSc programme and associated didactic materials.	If national recognition is delayed, MSc will be offered under existing institutional accreditation mechanisms.
Availability of EE training material	KIUT	The new training materials will be available on the GREENDT e-learning platform.	If the e-Learning platform becomes inactive, materials will be hosted on partner HEI websites or shared via academic repositories.
Adoption of models, methods, and resources in other fields	ASTI, CAGU, FSTU, JizPI, KIUT, MEEPCC, MHESI	Educational standards, curricula, teaching materials, methodologies, and tools developed in EE training could be applied to other MSc programmes in the Central Asia region, beyond the project's scope.	If institutional uptake is limited, GREENDT resources will be promoted through policy briefs and academic networks.
Project website	FEUGA KIUT FSTU	The Project website will be maintained for at least two years after the project's lifetime, displaying updates from GREENDT's e-learning platform for EE and the E-Society Platform.	Partners will host archived copies and migrate resources to local platforms once the central site becomes inactive.

4.2.1 Financial Sustainability Considerations

The sustainability of key GREENDT outcomes, including the EE MSc programme, the EE labs, the E-Society Platform, and the e-learning platform for EE, relies on a combination of institutional commitment, national-level policy integration, and funding opportunities.

The financial sustainability model is based on the following elements:

- **Institutional budgeting:** Uzbek HEIs involved in the project (ASTI, CAGU, FSTU, JizPI, KIUT) will review the allocation of internal resources (staff time, infrastructure support, IT

services) to maintain the MSc programme, the EE labs, the E-Society, and the e-Learning Platform for EE.

- **Public funding opportunities:** Engagements with MHESI and MEEPCC aim to secure public funding and integration into national budgets, especially for EE lab maintenance and student mobility schemes.
- **Cost-sharing arrangements:** For cross-institutional platforms (e.g., e-learning and E-Society), maintenance responsibilities and hosting costs will be explored among partner institutions based on sustainability agreements.
- **Follow-up projects and grants:** Partners will jointly explore funding from Erasmus+ Horizon Europe or national calls to support long-term research, curriculum innovation, and mobility.

These elements will be evaluated by M18, M30, and M36, and will inform the reviewed Exploitation and Sustainability Plan accordingly.

5 Monitoring and evaluation

To ensure long-term sustainability of GREENDT results, a structured monitoring and evaluation framework is embedded within the project lifecycle. This framework includes defined Communication and Dissemination KPIs (detailed in D7.1), internal progress reviews, and a risk register tracking external dependencies.

5.1 Monitoring exploitation and sustainability activities

Monitoring covers exploitation activities, focusing on uptake, relevance, and alignment with project goals. To ensure effective monitoring and implementation of the GREENDT sustainability and exploitation strategy, three interrelated actions types -Strategic Planning, Collaboration and Partnerships, and Policy Impact- will be embedded across key Work Packages (WPs) and their respective deliverables. The following table indicates where these actions will be specifically addressed.

Table 3. Mapping of Sustainability and Exploitation Actions to Project Deliverables, and the responsible partner

Action Type	Partner	Deliverable	Description	Timeline
Strategic Planning	JizPI	D2.2 – EE Strategic Plan Report	Incorporates long-term academic and institutional strategies based on stakeholder analysis, supporting academic and societal value creation.	M12
	ASTI	D6.1 – EE Master Study Plans Report	Embeds sustainability considerations in the development of the MSc program structure and objectives.	M12
	ASTI	D6.3 – Accreditation and Implementation Documents	Supports long-term program sustainability through formal integration into national academic systems.	M30
Collaboration and Partnerships	FSTU	D4.2 – EE Collaborative Network Report	Documents creating a transnational network of academic, industry, and policy actors to ensure ongoing collaboration and resource sharing.	M24
	KIUT	D5.4 – Minutes of Understanding for International Cooperation	Formalizes institutional partnerships and outlines future cooperation frameworks beyond the project's lifespan.	M34
Policy Impact	KIUT	D5.1 – Training Sessions Conclusion Report	Captures knowledge transfer efforts to influence national and institutional environmental and education policies.	M18
	KIUT	D5.2 – Webinars	Documents engagement with key stakeholders and	M24

Action Type	Partner	Deliverable	Description	Timeline
		Conclusion Report	polymakers through capacity-building events.	
	FEUGA	D7.2 – Sustainability and Exploitation Plan	Consolidates strategies for long-term impact, including stakeholder engagement and alignment with policy frameworks.	M6
	FEUGA	D7.4 / D7.5 – Dissemination Activities Reports	Highlights targeted outreach to decision-makers and broader stakeholder communities to support policy uptake of project outcomes.	M18/M36

All partners are expected to contribute to the above deliverables, ensuring that the sustainability and exploitation strategy is effectively implemented, tracked, and adapted as needed throughout the project lifecycle. Progress will be reviewed through internal milestones and reflected in WP7 reporting outputs.

5.1.1 Actions to Monitor Exploitation Activities

To track the progress and effectiveness of exploitation efforts, the following monitoring actions will be implemented:

- **Periodic Uptake Analysis:** Assess the adoption of project results by stakeholders every 6 months (M12, M18, M24, M30, M36).
- **Stakeholder Engagement Surveys:** Evaluate relevance and satisfaction of key stakeholders through short feedback surveys post-events (training, webinars in alignment with the Communication and Dissemination Plan..
- **Exploitation Readiness Scorecard:** Internal tool to rate the maturity of exploitable results and readiness for scale-up or policy adoption (reviewed at M18, M30).
- **KPI Dashboard Reporting:** Monitored and reported via WP7 to measure impact against defined dissemination and exploitation KPIs.
- **Annual Exploitation Workshops (M18 &M30):** Internal consortium events to share lessons learned, assess barriers, and update exploitation roadmaps.

Table 4 Risks to Project Exploitation and Mitigation Actions

Risks to Project Exploitation and Mitigation Actions	Evaluation point	Mitigation actions
Lack of stakeholder interest in exploiting project outputs	M18/M30	Conduct early and continuous stakeholder engagement (webinars, interviews); co-develop outputs with end-users; include stakeholders in WP reviews.
Low visibility of exploitable results beyond academia	M18 / M30	Target non-academic channels (industry, public sector); tailor dissemination materials (e.g. policy briefs, use cases); use FEUGA's exploitation plan.
Unclear hosting and maintenance of the E-learning platform for EE after project	M18	Establish a clear IPR management framework early (see D7.2); include licensing terms for digital and training assets.
Lack of coordination between partners on exploitation opportunities	M18 / M30	Set up a shared Exploitation Task Force; define responsibilities and procedures for

Risks to Project Exploitation and Mitigation Actions	Evaluation point	Mitigation actions
		follow-up on potential joint ventures or spin-offs.
No long-term host or business model for key project outputs	M24–M30	Assign responsible partners for hosting/maintenance (e.g., e-platforms); explore commercialization models or integration into institutional services.
Weak alignment of outputs with policy or market needs	M18 / M30	Validate outputs with policy and market actors regularly; use WP5 and WP7 engagement activities to align project outcomes with current demand.
Insufficient funding sources to scale exploitation post-project	M30	Identify national/EU funding schemes for post-project scale-up; include sustainability costs in institutional strategic plans.

5.1.2 Additional Recommendations to Support Exploitation

- Include **exploitation-readiness criteria** in deliverable quality reviews.
- Host a **final exploitation workshop** with external stakeholders (M34–M36) to showcase outcomes and define next steps.
- Develop **exploitation factsheets** for each key result (target, owner, use cases, scalability potential).

5.2 Evaluation of exploitation and sustainability activities

Evaluation will be driven by review checkpoints, and its outcome will be reflected in the final Sustainability and Exploitation Plan iteration (M36). The GREENDT consortium plans to organise two checkpoints by M18 and M30 before finalising the exploitation roadmap, by M36. The main objective sought by these checkpoints is to assess the dependencies and risks, and serve as a decision point to activate mitigation strategies and contingency plans if necessary.

Risk management will be integrated through a shared register of risks that might affect the project results' sustainability with clear mitigation pathways, and reviewed at M18, M30, and M36.

Table 5 Risks for the sustainability of project results and mitigation actions

Risks for the sustainability of project results	Decision point	Mitigation actions to ensure sustainability
EE MSc not accredited nationally by MHESI	M30	Proceed with institutional-level MSc implementation; maintain policy engagement; involve ministries in pilot review
Unclear financial sustainability for the EE labs after project	M30	Embed lab operations in institutional strategies and explore national/international co-funding
Unclear hosting and maintenance of the E-learning platform for EE after project	M30	Host under KIUT with shared responsibility from other HEIs; integrate in their digital strategies

Risks for the sustainability of project results	Decision point	Mitigation actions to ensure sustainability
Stakeholder disengagement	M34	Sign sustainability MoUs before project end; maintain ongoing communication through E-Society platform
Low MSc student enrollment	M24–M36	Launch outreach campaigns, ensure job-market relevance, involve employers in curriculum feedback

6 Conclusions

The GREENDT sustainability and exploitation strategy has been established, outlining the project's expected results, how these will be utilized, and who will carry on the exploitation after the project's conclusion. This initial version of the GREENDT sustainability and exploitation plan presents a preliminary list of exploitation activities aligned with the defined strategy. Project partners will carry out these activities during the project's duration.

This plan includes a summary of the GREENDT impact indicators. These indicators are especially valuable for ensuring the sustainability and exploitation strategy meets its objectives and supporting the effective implementation of planned activities.

This plan recognises that the long-term sustainability of several Key Exploitable Results (KERs) depends on reaching agreements with national ministries, higher education institutions' leadership, and other stakeholders. Given these dependencies, this strategy integrates conditional planning, risk monitoring, and periodic review points. Implementation actions are tracked with milestone-based assessments and adjusted accordingly to ensure that GREENDT results can remain impactful even in the absence of the necessary conditions.

To support effective monitoring and evaluation, the plan incorporates a structured data-gathering methodology, as described in Section 5. Each exploitation and sustainability-related action is linked to specific indicators and checkpoints. Data sources include project deliverables, survey feedback from stakeholders, and progress reports submitted by WP leads. These data will be reviewed periodically, enabling the project team to track performance, assess feasibility, and adapt strategies accordingly.

This first version of the Sustainability and Exploitation Plan establishes a structured but adaptive framework to guide GREENDT partners in pursuing the long-term use of project results. Recognising that some outcomes depend on external commitments from ministries and national stakeholders, the plan integrates conditional pathways and risk mitigation strategies. Implementation and stakeholder engagement will be monitored throughout the project using defined indicators. A revised, results-based plan will be produced at M36, reflecting actual uptake and institutional commitments reached during the project.